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Subtle response in Arctic coastal benthos to environmental change - a case study from NE Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland)

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Climate change is rapidly altering the environment in the Arctic with large implications for marine life. This study presents the first time-series analysis of epibenthic community structure in Young Sound, NE Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland), aiming to assess the structural and functional changes over time in response to climate-driven environmental change. Using data collected by drop cameras and ROVs at depths of 20m to 60m, from years 2003–2010 and 2021–2022, we evaluated the taxonomic and functional composition of the benthic community. Brittle stars and bivalves were the most common taxa, altogether comprising 95% of total abundances, and they displayed fluctuating temporal trend, with a significant reduction in bivalve abundances in the later years. Dissimilarities in the benthic communities were primarily driven by differences in depth and secondly by the length of the open water period. Longer ice-free period led to an increase in the large and small size classes, short-lived and filter/suspension feeding taxa, which may impact higher trophic levels in the fjord. This shift indicates that ecosystem changes are also occurring in the outflow region of the Arctic, underscoring the vulnerability of Arctic benthic ecosystems to climate change.

KEYWORDS

Arctic, benthos, change, coastal, ecology, fjord, marine, traits

1 Introduction

Anthropogenic climate change is rapidly unfolding, with every ecosystem impacted by human activity, including in remote Arctic coasts (Lewis and Maslin, 2015). Many ecosystems have likely already experienced pronounced changes as a result of climate change, prior to the scientific community gaining a solid understanding of their structure and function. Climate change is particularly alarming in the Arctic (Rantanen et al., 2022), where the warming has already been observed to cause reductions in sea-ice cover, with an average of 10% loss in sea ice extent per decade since 1970 (Årthun et al., 2021) and accelerating loss of glaciers and ice sheets (Hugonnet et al., 2021), as well as a freshening of the fjord waters (Sejr et al., 2017) and ocean acidification (Thyrring et al., 2023). While shifting water masses (Atlantification) is particularly pronounced along the West coast of Svalbard (Ingvaldsen et al., 2021), changes in water mass distribution has been more subtle

along the NE coast of Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland) (Gjelstrup et al., 2022), although recent changes in water masses and sea ice distribution have been identified as the major drivers in the biological regime shift observed along the SE Kalaallit Nunaat coast (Heide-Jorgensen et al., 2023).

Coastal ecosystems are expected to be more heavily impacted by climate change compared to the open ocean as changes in catchments and run-off affect the flow of organic matter and nutrients to the coastal ocean (Sejr et al., 2024). Reduced sea-ice cover and increased run-off change the light penetration in the water column (Schlegel et al., 2024), increase coastal erosion (Nielsen et al., 2022) and wave-action (Overeem et al., 2011), and change sedimentation and primary production patterns (Attard et al., 2024). As a result, coastal areas are impacted by multiple drivers resulting in a complex mosaic of pressures. For Kalaallit Nunaat, this means that the NE and SE coasts are hotspots of cumulative environmental change. Although several studies document that climate change induces substantial biological changes in this region, there are important knowledge gaps especially at lower trophic levels and related to biodiversity in general (Ager et al., 2025).

Benthos, organisms that live on, in, and near the sea-bottom constitute a crucial component of the Arctic marine system and they can be used as an indicator of environmental change, since many have limited mobility, slow growth, and a long lifespan, which likely increases vulnerability to environmental change (Beuchel et al., 2006). Benthos provides key ecosystem functions like ecosystem engineering and bioturbation (Weinert et al., 2022), as well as energy and matter transfer (Lam-Gordillo et al., 2020), hence structural and functional changes in benthic communities will likely impact higher trophic levels. Biological traits, a set of measurable properties of an organism often related to the morphological, behavioral, and life history characteristics, can be used to assess a species' impact on the functioning of an ecosystem (Bremner et al., 2006) and by linking species abundance and traits, functional changes to the ecosystem across time and space can be illuminated (Armitage et al., 2024). Alterations in benthic communities have already been documented in the Arctic (Calvet et al., 2024) and include shifts in biogeography and phenology (Burrows et al., 2011), an upward and northward expansion in macroalgae (Krause-Jensen et al., 2020) and associated reorganization in invertebrate community (Kortsch et al., 2012; Al-Hababeh et al., 2020), borealization (Husson et al., 2024), altered benthic community biomass and production (Paar et al., 2015), as well as trait composition (Al-Hababeh et al., 2020), all of which can ultimately lead to sensitivity to species invasions. The documented changes have been linked to climate change, but are also contingent on local environmental conditions, such as the substrate type, depth, and location in the fjord, and food availability (Kędra et al., 2011; Jorda-Molina et al., 2023). The benthic community is highly influenced by pelagic processes exporting organic material to it through the benthic-pelagic coupling, so benthos can also serve as an indicator of changed pelagic hydrography (Pavlova et al., 2023).

The benthic ecosystems along the coast of NE Kalaallit Nunaat are amongst the least studied regions in the Arctic (Zwerschke et al., 2025) due to the isolation, remoteness, and logistical challenges associated with conducting research in this region. Young Sound in

NE Kalaallit Nunaat houses the only marine research station in the region, Daneborg, and work there has greatly advanced our knowledge on biogeochemical properties of fjord systems through the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring program (Christensen and Arndal, 2025). Research has been conducted from Daneborg since 1996, with the monitoring program established in 2003 to study sea-ice cover and biogeochemical properties such as water temperature, salinity, nutrient concentrations, phytoplankton and zooplankton biomass and composition, through annual sampling in the summer combined with year-round mooring data. Benthos is not included in the monitoring program, but several studies have provided valuable information on benthic invertebrate diversity (Bridier et al., 2024; Sejr et al., 2000), benthic carbon dynamics (Glud et al., 2000; Attard et al., 2016), and selected fauna such as brittle stars (Blicher and Sejr, 2011), and the bivalve *Hiatella arctica* (Sejr et al., 2002) in Young Sound, and in the wider region of the NE Kalaallit Nunaat coast, shelf, and slope (Fredriksen et al., 2020) (Piepenburg and Schmid, 1996; Piepenburg et al., 1997). These studies provide a comprehensive baseline of information for a sparsely studied region but have not monitored the benthic community over time. Time-series are crucial to further our understanding of the natural variability versus the climate-forced change in Arctic ecosystems (Wassmann, 2011), but few exist for benthic communities (for overview of time-series, see table in Renaud et al., 2015b).

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study was conducted from the research station Daneborg in Young Sound (74°18'N, 20°18'W), NE Kalaallit Nunaat (Figure 1) each summer over the period 2003–2010 and again in 2021–2022. Young Sound is a 90 km long, 2–7 km wide fjord located in an East-West direction with a maximum depth of 340m and a 40–50m sill at the entrance (Sejr and Christensen, 2007) (Figure 1a). The fjord is estimated to receive a total of 0.9–1.4 km³ meltwater input per year, with 50–80% of this originating from the land-terminating glaciers creating a strong pycnocline at 5–10m (Citterio et al., 2017; Meire et al., 2017). Low rates of primary production, with an estimate of only 10g C m⁻² per year makes Young Sound one of the least productive coastal ecosystems in the world (Holding et al., 2019).

Biogeochemical parameters have been monitored in the fjord since 2003 through the MarinBasis monitoring program and are publicly available (Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring 2024). Sea ice thickness reaches its maximum of 150 cm in April, and a thick snow layer attenuates the incoming solar radiation in spring and early summer, thereby limiting primary production (Attard et al., 2016). The fjord is ice-free only in July–October and the number of open water days range from 64 to 145 days between the years 1950 and 2022. Ice-melt and break-up in July sparks primary production which increases vertical export of organic matter, as well as benthic remineralization (Attard et al., 2016; Holding et al., 2019). Euphotic depth, defined as the depth of 1% surface irradiance, is located between 25m and 40m during the open water period, as measured

FIGURE 1

Map of study area. (a) Young Sound, Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland) with the three transects marked as H1-3 image credit Copernicus Sentinel-2 data for August 2022. (b) Map of Atlantic sector of the Arctic Ocean indicating the geographic context.

near Daneborg in summer of 2011 (Meire et al., 2017). Circulation inside the fjord is generally limited by the shallow sill with a depth of 45m (Boone et al., 2017) and the fjord is influenced by the East Greenland Current (EGC) which transports sea ice and cold low saline Polar Water (PW) southwards from the Arctic Ocean (Gjelstrup et al., 2022), but renewal of the fjord basin water happens at a slow rate. A mooring deployed at 50m depth has registered a decrease in salinity with approximately 1 psu over the study period (Figure 2a), whereas the water temperature has increased by an average of 0.5 °C (Figure 2b).

2.2 Environmental data

Data on ice cover, open water period, mooring temperature and salinity were obtained from MarinBasis (Greenland Ecosystem

Monitoring, 2024), from the area of the fjord in front of Daneborg, close to transect H2 (Figure 1). Freshwater runoff data were obtained from a model that calculates the total runoff in the whole fjord (Mankoff et al., 2020). This study covers the period that experienced the largest change since 1950.

2.3 Photographic sampling and analysis

Sampling was conducted in August-September during the study period, at three different depths (20m, 40m and 60m) in three different transects (H1-H3) with a decreasing distance from the fjord mouth (Figure 1a). The photographic sampling was performed with a drop-camera or a remotely operated vehicle (ROV). The drop camera used in the years 2003–2010 was a Nikon D100 camera with a 20 mm lens and an APS-C CCD sensor with a size of 23.7 * 15.6 mm, mounted in a waterproof housing together with two underwater lights and two lasers to provide scale in each image. Image resolution was 3000 x 2000 pixels. In years 2021 and 2022, photographic sampling was conducted with a FiFish pro V6 ROV plus. The ROV was equipped with lights and inbuilt lasers and was hovering above the sea floor at approximately 50cm distance to create as little disturbance as possible but providing the highest resolution possible. The wide-angle camera has a 1/2.3 inch CMOS camera sensor and pixel size of 3000 x 4000 pixels. The larger sensor of the Nikon camera compared to the ROV camera resulted in higher quality images of the earlier years compared to the images from years 2021–2022, despite the higher resolution of images from the later years. All images were saved as a JPG files and processed in Adobe Photoshop 2025 after adjusting the hue, saturation, brightness, and contrast (see Beuchel et al., 2010 for details). An average area of 1.0 m² (± 0.3 m² SD) was analyzed from each depth, transect, and year.

Three images from each transect and depth were analyzed for taxon abundances, percent cover of macroalgae, substrate type (visually categorized to the following categories 1, <1% hard substrate; 2, 1-10%; 3, >10-50%; 4, >50%) and microphytobenthos (category 1, <1% cover; 2, 1-5%; 3, >5-20%; 4, >20-50%; 5, >50%). All visible invertebrates were counted and identified to the lowest taxonomic level possible, and their average abundance was calculated per square meter. A taxonomic image catalogue was produced and confirmed by experts (listed in the acknowledgments) to ensure

FIGURE 2

Mean seawater salinity (a) and seawater temperature (b) at 50m depth in Young Sound, Kalaallit Nunaat from year 2003–2022. Loess smooth regression lines in red for salinity and blue for temperature with associated confidence intervals. Dark gray shaded areas cover years used in this study (2003–2010 and 2021–2022).

accurate and consistent identification. All taxonomic names were updated to the currently accepted names (WoRMS Editorial Board, 2026). Small individuals were likely underestimated due to the difference in image quality resulting from the different camera system used, therefore, some of the smaller taxa, such as small polychaetes, were excluded from the analysis, as well as highly mobile animals, like mysids and fish, were also excluded since they were not reliably sampled.

In images where brittle stars were present in high numbers (>100 individuals), only animals in 25% of the image area were counted by overlaying the image with a grid of one hundred squares, counting brittle stars in every fourth square, and then multiplying the obtained number by 4. If a brittle star covered two or more grids, the animal was included in the grid where the majority of the disc was located. Very rare taxa, present in less than three samples (at each depth and transect for each given year) were excluded from the analyses of community data. Individuals that could not be reliably identified were grouped to a higher taxonomic level, such as Styelidae tunicates and Sabellidae polychaetes. After exclusion and grouping of the 55 originally identified taxa, a total of 33 different invertebrate taxa were included in the analysis.

2.4 Functional traits data

The functional changes in the community were investigated using a trait-based analysis of fuzzy coded trait modalities for each taxon obtained from the Arctic Traits Database (Degen and Faulwetter, 2019) or supplemented from literature where lacking. Traits considered to be most important in the functioning of the ecosystem and potentially affected by an altered climate were selected based on the literature (Bremner et al., 2006; Degen et al., 2018; Al-Hababeh et al., 2020) and fuzzy coded with values ranging between 0 to 3 (Degen and Faulwetter, 2019) (Supplementary Data Sheet). A trait value of 0 indicated that a taxon did not exhibit a given trait and a value of 3 implied that the taxon largely expressed the given trait and intermediate values of 1–2 indicated that a given taxon could express several trait modalities (Chevene et al., 1994). When no information on trait expressions could be obtained, the given trait modality was coded with 0.

2.5 Data analysis

The biodiversity indices calculated in the study included Shannon's H' index with natural logarithm base, Simpson diversity index and Pielou's evenness.

The spatial and temporal variation in benthic community data was explored by Correspondence Analysis (CA) to identify the main gradients of structural variation, integrating environmental information in the associated biplots. The effects of habitat heterogeneity and climate variability on community structure were modelled by a Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA), followed by permutation analyses for significance testing of overall and marginal effects of environmental variables. Community data were square-root transformed to downplay the importance of the very abundant taxa in the CA and CCA outcomes. The environmental variables included in the CCA were depth, transect,

substrate, and number of open water days. Runoff, sea temperature, and salinity data were excluded from the analysis due to their high collinearity with the other predictors.

For the trait-based analysis, community-weighted means (CWM) were computed to obtain a trait-characterization of communities, weighing the trait data by the square-root transformed abundances. The spatial variation and temporal changes in CWM were illustrated as proportions of trait modalities over time and summarized by a CA biplot.

All plots, taxonomic diversity indices, and statistical analyses were performed in R (R Core Team, 2026). The CA, CCA and permutation analyses were implemented using the vegan package (Oksanen et al., 2025), graphs were plotted with the ggplot2 package (Wickham, 2016), and the map was plotted with the ggOceanMaps package (Vihtakari, 2026).

3 Results

3.1 Habitat and environmental characteristics

The duration of the ice-free season and the runoff in Young Sound both showed an increasing trend starting around the year 2000 (Figures 3a, b). From the year 1950 to 2000 the average ice-free season was 83.5 days (SD 7.6), and the modelled fjord-wide run-off was 5921 m³/sec (SD 1630). From 2000 to 2022 the open water period increased by 25% to an average of 104.5 days (SD 19.2) and the modelled run-off increased by over 50% to 9023 m³/sec (SD 2038).

The prevalence of hard substrate decreased towards the mouth of the fjord, with the highest proportion of hard substrate found at the innermost transect H1 and the lowest at the outermost transect H3 (Supplementary Figure 1). The substrate distribution along each transect was uniform throughout the study period, except for 2006 when the amount of visible hard substrate in the photographs dropped at 20m and 40m in transect H1, likely due to macroalgae covering the substrate. It increased at 40m in transect H3.

Microphytobenthos was present at all depths and transects in relatively high concentrations throughout the whole study period (Supplementary Figure 1). In 2006, there was a drop in microphytobenthos cover in transect H1 at 20m and an increase in H3 at 20m. The outermost transect H3 showed the highest, although variable, macroalgae cover among the three transects, with H2 having very low cover, except for 2021 and 2022 when the cover was substantially higher than in previous years, whereas macroalgae cover (Supplementary Figure 1) showed an opposite pattern, with an increase in H1 at 20m and a decrease in H3 at 20m.

3.2 Biodiversity and abundance

We identified a total of 55 taxa of invertebrates and 9 taxa of macroalgae belonging to 11 different phyla (Figure 4). Mollusca displayed the highest taxonomic richness, but almost half of the identified taxa in this phylum were rare, occurring in less than three

FIGURE 3
 Changing environmental conditions in Young Sound, Kalaallit Nunaat over seven decades. **(a)** Open water period from 1950–2022 (black line) and **(b)** modelled fjord-wide run-off 1950–2022 (black line). Loess regression smooth line in red for open water period and green for runoff, with associated confidence intervals in pink and green respectively. Dark gray shaded areas cover years used in this study (2003–2010 and 2021–2022). Data is obtained from the MarinBasis program of (Greenland Ecosystem monitoring, 2024).

samples. Echinodermata and Arthropoda shared the second rank on taxon richness followed by Chordata, Cnidaria and Rhodophyta. Echinoderms displayed the highest abundances at all depths, with abundance increasing with depth, whereas Mollusca, the second most abundant phylum, showed decreasing abundances with depth (Supplementary Figure 2).

The biodiversity was relatively low, with Shannon’s H' of 0.66, Simpson diversity of 0.27, and Pielou’s evenness was also low with $J = 0.16$. All of the indices displayed an overall decreasing trend over the study period (Supplementary Figure 3).

Brittle stars and bivalves accounted for over 95% of the total invertebrate abundance. The most abundant taxa by far were the brittle stars, *Ophiocten sericeum* and *Ophiura robusta* (combined in analysis

FIGURE 4
 Total number of taxa in each phylum identified in Young Sound images between year 2003 and 2022 across all depths and transects.

since they could not be separated in the images), which were most numerous at deeper depths, reaching a maximum of 885.5 ind./m² (60m at H3 in 2008) in one sample (Figure 5). The average combined abundance across all years and transects for the two species was 74.6 ind./m² (SD 70.8) at 20m, 303.0 ind./m² (SD 149.2) at 40m, and 404.3 ind./m² (SD 209.1) at 60m (Table 1). In 2006, brittle star abundance increased substantially at 60m in the innermost transect, H1, with a corresponding reduction at 40m in the same transect, whereas a substantial drop in abundance was recorded at 60m in transect H3 (Figures 6a–c). The second-most abundant taxa were the bivalves *Mya* sp. and *Hiatella arctica* (combined since not separable in images), which were most prevalent at 20m, with an average combined abundance across all years and transects of 62.2 ind./m² (SD 45.2) at 20m, 31.9 ind./m² (SD 22.0) at 40m and 7.5 ind./m² (SD 8.9) at 60m (Table 1). Bivalve distribution also showed a fluctuation pattern over time, with a pronounced increase in abundance at 20m in the year 2006 at both H1 and H3 transects (Figures 6 d–f). Overall, bivalve abundances decreased significantly over time (Welch t-test, $df = 18.79$, $t = 2.64$, p -value = 0.02).

The next most abundant taxa were the hard substrate associated limpet *Lepeta caeca*, which displayed a patchy distribution and was most common at 40m with an average of 3.8 ind./m² (SD 4.6), and the Greenland clam *Similipecten greenlandicus*, Margaritidae snails and the sea cucumber *Psolus* sp., which were most common at 40 and 60m (Table 1). Less common taxa included, in decreasing order of abundance, Ascidiacea, *Strongylocentrotus* sp., *Heliometra glacialis*, *Hormathia* sp., Buccinidae, *Nymphon* sp., *Ciona intestinalis*, Decapoda, *Balanus balanus*, *Ptychogasteria polaris*, sediment-covered Pectinida, *Synarachnactis lloydii*, Sabellidae, and *Munnopsis* sp. Rare taxa that were only present in 5 or less images included *Ophiopholis aculeata*, *Ophiopleura borealis*, *Sclerocrangon* sp., Malacalcyonacea, *Arcturus baffini*, Asteriidae, *Crossaster* sp., morphotype 1, morphotype 2, *Astarte* sp., Edwardsiidae, Polyplacophora, and morphotype Porifera.

3.3 Variation in benthic community structure between habitats

Habitat heterogeneity led to distinct benthic communities in the fjord. Depth was associated with the main CA gradient of community structure (CA axis I) which accounted for 14% of the total variation in community structure (Figure 7). The importance of depth in structuring benthic communities was confirmed by the CCA, where depth was aligned with the first ordination axis accounting for 11.9% of the variation (Figure 8) and contributed significantly to benthic variation (Permutation test of marginal effect, $p=0.001$). The communities at 20m depth were dominated by the Sabellidae, Buccinidae, Ascidiacea, and the bivalves *H. arctica* and *Mya* sp. The communities at 40m depth were characterized by Margaritidae, *P. polaris*, Decapoda, *Strongylocentrotus* sp., and Pectinidae, whereas the deepest communities were characterized by the brittle stars *O. sericeum* and *O. robusta*, *Hormathia* sp., *L.caeca*, *Nymphon* sp., and *Psolus* sp. (Figures 7, 8).

Location in the fjord (transects H1–H3) also affected the benthic community structure significantly (Permutation test of marginal effect, $p=0.001$) as did substrate type (Permutation test of marginal effect, $p=0.001$). Overall, the CCA model accounted for 36% of the total variation in benthic community structure.

FIGURE 5
High densities of brittle stars at 60m in 2008 in transect H3. The image area covers 0.369 m².

3.4 Community variability over time associated with environmental change

The temporal variation in benthic community structure was associated with the open water period, which aligned with the second axis of the CA and CCA (Figures 7, 8). Taxa associated with increased open water period were the Pectinidae, Buccinidae snails, and the polychaete family Sabellidae, as well as several of the taxa with low abundances, such as the isopod *A. baffini*, ascidian *C. intestinalis*, sea anemones Edwardsiidae and *S. lloydii*, the feather star *H. glacialis*, and brittle star *O. borealis*. The open water period had a significant effect on the benthic community structure in the CCA (Permutation test of marginal effect, $p < 0.001$).

The benthic community responded differently to the climate pressure depending on the substrate type, as indicated by the significant interaction term between substrate and number of open water days (Permutation test of marginal effect, $p < 0.001$).

3.5 Functional characterization

The most common trait modalities across all depths in Young Sound benthos were small/medium body size, 5–20-year life span, low mobility, filter/suspension and surface deposit feeding modes, soft substrate affinity, intermediate stress tolerance, and Arctic/Boreal biogeography.

Trait modalities were found to change over time, with the largest change generally observed in the shallowest communities. Body size at 20m and 40m displayed an increase in the small/medium modality and a decrease in the medium body size in later years, and the large body size was only present in the years 2005, 2021, and 2022 at all depths (Figure 9). Organisms with a life span of >20 years were decreased in the later years (2021–2022) at all depths, whereas the 5–20-year trait modality increased in those years (Figure 9). Low mobility in the community was the most common trait, followed by medium mobility, and no mobility (Supplementary Figure 4). Filter suspension feeders were most common at 20m and 40m, and this feeding mode was present to a smaller degree in 2008 and 2021–2022, corresponding to the years with the highest runoff during the study period (Figure 3b). In those years, the community exhibited a higher proportion of benthos with predator and surface/deposit feeding traits. In the 60m community, surface/deposit feeding was the most common feeding strategy, followed by predation and opportunist/scavenging (Figure 9).

Communities at all depths showed a preferred substrate affinity for soft bottom, followed by hard-bottom and biological substrate (Supplementary Figure 4), whereas the most common stress-tolerance trait modality was intermediate, followed by low disturbance tolerance, across all depths (Supplementary Figure 4). High disturbance tolerance was present at low levels but to a variable degree over the years at all depths, whereas the most common biogeography modality across all

TABLE 1 Average abundances (ind./m²) of the 6 most abundant taxa at each depth, across all years, standard deviation in brackets.

Depth	<i>O. sericeum</i> & <i>O. robusta</i>	<i>Mya</i> sp. & <i>H. arctica</i>	<i>Lepeta caeca</i>	<i>S. greenlandicus</i>	Margaritidae	<i>Psolus</i> sp.
20m	74.6 (± 70.8)	62.2 (± 45.2)	0.1 (± 0.6)	2.0 (± 3.3)	1.1 (± 2.9)	0.0 (± 0.2)
40m	303.0 (± 149.2)	31.9 (± 22.0)	3.8 (± 4.6)	1.7 (± 3.1)	2.5 (± 3.5)	1.9 (± 2.7)
60m	404.3 (± 209.1)	7.5 (8.9)	1.6 (± 2.7)	3.2 (± 6.2)	0.5 (± 1.0)	1.9 (± 2.7)

FIGURE 6 Abundances of the dominant taxa in Young Sound images. Brittle stars *O. sericeum* and *O. robusta* (a–c) and bivalves *Mya* sp. and *H. arctica* abundances (d–f) per square meter from year 2003–2010 and 2021–2022 in transect H1 (a, d) and transect H2 (b, e) and transect H3 (c, f). Standard deviation is shown in lighter color.

FIGURE 7 Correspondence analysis (CA) biplot of benthic community structure in Young Sound. The symbols illustrate the benthic community at a given transect (shape) and depth (color). The numeric labels next to the symbol correspond to the sampling year (3–10: 2003–2010 and 21–22: 2021–2022). The cyan colored labels depict the tip of the vectors for the benthic taxa and sites with taxa present in less than 10 sites have a smaller font and are colored gray (see [Supplementary Data Sheet](#) for abbreviations)

FIGURE 8

Canonical Correspondence analysis (CCA) triplot of benthic community structure in Young Sound. The symbols illustrate the benthic community at a given transect (shape) and depth (color). The numeric labels next to the symbol correspond to the sampling year (3–10: 2003–2010 and 21–22: 2021–2022). The labels depicting the tip of the vectors for environmental drivers are colored black (open water days - OWD, interaction between substrate S and OWD - OS1.5–OS4), gray (transect H1–H3), and brown (substrate S1–4). The cyan colored labels depict the tip of the vectors for the benthic taxa and sites with taxa present in less than 10 sites have a smaller font and are colored gray (see [Supplementary Data Sheet](#) for abbreviations).

depths was the Arctic/Boreal biogeography, followed by Arctic and Cosmopolitan. Boreal taxa were only present in years 2003, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2021 ([Supplementary Figure 4](#)) corresponding to the later years and years with a longer open water period ([Figure 3a](#)).

The first two CA axes of the community-weighted means accounted for 69% of the variance ([Figure 10](#)) and depicted a pattern similar to that observed in the biplots of taxonomic data ([Figures 7, 8](#)). The first CA axis accounted for 58% of the variation and was associated with differences in depth whereas the second CA axis summarized 10.6% of the variation and was associated with the open water period. The years associated with a longer open water period were characterized by a community with a greater prevalence of Boreal taxa with a large and large/medium body size, relatively short (2–5-year) life span, and a high disturbance tolerance.

4 Discussion

Our study highlights the importance of habitat heterogeneity in structuring coastal benthic communities in Arctic fjords as well as its role in modulating responses to climate variability. Epibenthic composition and abundance were strongly influenced by depth and substrate type. With increasing depth, the abundance of brittle stars *Ophiocten sericeum* and *Ophiura robusta* increased, and that of bivalves *Mya* sp. and *Hiatella arctica* decreased. Depth is a main structuring factor in benthos, as it influences important physical and biological habitat characteristics including substrate type, light regime, nutrient and, importantly, food availability ([Ravelo et al., 2020](#); [Vedenin et al., 2022](#)). Community structure varied in

association with the duration of the open water period. Over time, the abundance of the bivalves *Mya* sp. and *H. arctica* decreased, whereas the boreal ascidian *Ciona intestinalis* was present only in years with a long open water period. The responses to the changing open water period were contingent on substrate type, with softer and harder sediment communities showing opposite trends. The difference in response was likely due to complex interactions between food availability, altered environmental conditions, as well as the life history of the benthic organisms, for example the limited mobility of hard substrate-attached taxa restricting the sessile invertebrates from moving up/down or in/out of the fjord to areas with more favorable conditions. The community-weighted mean trait modalities associated with a longer open water period indicated shifts away from the characteristic long-lived, filter/suspension feeding community.

4.1 Variation in community structure across habitats

Depth and substrate type were primary drivers of benthic community structure. The dominant brittle stars *O. sericeum* and *O. robusta* increased in density with depth, in agreement with earlier findings from Young Sound ([Sejr et al., 2000](#)). The two brittle star species are commonly found in high numbers in Arctic fjords and shelves, where their abundances increase with depth to about 100m whereafter they decline ([Piepenburg and Schmid, 1996](#); [Blicher and Sejr, 2011](#)). Their high abundances illustrate a brittle star community highly adapted to the low production of Young Sound, as they have very low carbon requirements ([Blicher and Sejr, 2011](#)). The surface feeder *O. sericeum*, is considered the most

FIGURE 9 Proportion of community-weighted trait means in the benthic community with 95% confidence intervals. Left plots depict communities at 20m, middle plots at 40m and right plots at 60m, and body size (a–c), lifespan (d–f) and feeding mode (g–i).

abundant in Young Sound and can feed at several trophic levels (Bridier et al., 2021b). Their mobility suggests that they can move between depths and favorable habitats when pulses of food become available, including large macroalgal detrital patches found deeper than where macroalgae grow (pers. obs.). This mechanism could explain the observed increase in the two most common brittle stars in transect H1 in 2006 coinciding with a local increase in macroalgae and detritus, and conversely the decrease in brittle star abundances in H3 coinciding with a local decrease in macroalgae.

The second most abundant group, the bivalves *H. arctica* and *Mya* sp., were present in highest densities at shallow depths and mean abundances were similar to those obtained by grab samples in an earlier study in Young Sound (Sejr et al., 2000). The decreasing densities with depth could be a result of predation by *O. sericeum* which has high abundances at deeper depths and has been found to predate on small

H. arctica individuals (Sejr et al., 2002), although this species is known to be mostly detritivorous (Wood et al., 2011). It could also be linked to the higher amount of hard substrate at shallower depths, as *H. arctica* prefers coarser substrate, whereas *Mya* spp. dominates in soft sediment. *H. arctica* is an important species in the subtidal ecosystem of Young Sound, where it grows slowly, living up to 126 years, and its carbon demand accounts for an estimated 3.6% of the pelagic production in the outer part of Young Sound (Sejr et al., 2002).

Location within the fjord also resulted in distinct communities, with the three transects displaying significantly different community compositions, possibly due to differences between the amount of hard substrate. The high concentration of microphytobenthos across all transects and down to 60m throughout the study period, is consistent with previous studies in Young Sound (Attard et al., 2016) and is likely due to the algae’s adaptation to low light levels. The generally high cover could suggest that microphytobenthos,

FIGURE 10

Fuzzy Correspondence Analysis (CA) biplot of community-weighted means of traits and taxonomic abundance of the benthic community in Young Sound. The symbols illustrate the benthic community at a given transect (shape) and depth (color). The numeric labels next to the symbol correspond to the sampling year (3–10: 2003–2010 and 21–22: 2021–2022). The cyan colored labels depict the tip of the vectors for the trait modalities (see [Supplementary Data Sheet](#) for abbreviations).

rather than phytoplankton, might be an abundant food source that could sustain benthos (see further discussion below), potentially supporting a community resilient to changes in ice cover and turbidity from run-off.

Generally, taxonomic composition of the epibenthos in the study region was comparable to that of other Arctic coastal areas including those in inflow shelves in terms of the numerical dominance of brittle stars, and the occurrence of widespread species across phyla (Sswat et al., 2015; Jørgensen et al., 2015). While a detailed comparison is limited by differences in approaches, small observed differences warrant further study: The present study found very low densities of decapods and in particular no crabs were found in this study compared to Arctic inflow areas, where *Hyas*, *Chionoecetes* and hermit crabs are common or have increased (Gulliksen and Svensen, 2004; Bluhm et al., 2009). Very low bottom water temperatures, as observed in the study area, have until recently set physiological limits to crab occurrence in Antarctica, but warming is anticipated to remove that barrier to these predators (Aronson et al., 2015; Aronson et al., 2007). Expansion of predators is known to have restructured food webs on Arctic shelves (Kortsch et al., 2015). We, therefore, recommend particular attention be given to monitoring crab abundance in addition to the ratio of Arctic to boreal invertebrates, as potential indicators of system change in NE Kalaallit Nunaat fjords.

4.2 Community variability associated with environmental change over time

The change in community structure associated with increased open water period indicates that benthos along the coastal outflow regions of the Arctic might already display climate-induced

community reorganization. Subtle shifts in community structure were evident in individual taxa as well as at the whole-community level. The most notable change was the occurrence of the ascidian *C. intestinalis*, only in the years with a longer open water period, an opportunistic and fouling species, invasive in many parts of the world due to its wide environmental tolerance and capacity to withstand high turbidity (Vercaemer et al., 2011). Its limited larval dispersal capacities and 8 °C temperature limit for spawning (Carver et al., 2006) suggest that it does not reproduce in Young Sound but is likely transported to the fjord with currents or vessels and can only manage to establish when the environmental conditions favor it. With few benthic studies in the NE Greenland region, it is difficult to assess whether *C. intestinalis* is invasive there, but our results show that it has substantially increased in densities in the later years in Young Sound. In addition, *C. intestinalis* did not co-occur with the other ascidians in this study, which were more associated with the years with a shorter open water period, suggesting an effect of interspecific competition and different adaptabilities to altered environmental conditions. A negative trend in abundances of ascidians and anemones has been linked to climate warming in a Svalbard fjord, where increased sedimentation from terrestrial and glacial runoff is suggested to clog the feeding apparatus (Kortsch et al., 2012; Beuchel et al., 2006). Although sedimentation was not measured in the current study, declines of species with low tolerance to sedimentation could favor the more tolerant *C. intestinalis*, which could explain the observations in this study. In any case, the abundance of *C. intestinalis* should be closely monitored in the future, to determine if the species continue to increase in numbers in Young Sound and how this affects the other ascidians in the fjord, as *C. intestinalis* potentially could serve as an indicator of an altered turbidity regime.

Our findings also highlighted differences in response to increased open water period between bivalve species. Earlier work in Young Sound has linked increased open water period to elevated growth rates in bivalves (Sejr et al., 2009) and sea urchins (Blicher et al., 2007), ascribed to increased food availability through a longer productive season for phytoplankton. Our observations of higher abundances of *Similipecten greenlandicus*, as well as sediment-covered Pectinidae (likely also *S. greenlandicus*) in years with a longer open water period, are consistent with the above suggested interpretation (Jensen and Rasch, 2009). The most common bivalve species in Young Sound, *Mya* sp. and *H. arctica*, however, showed a decrease in abundances over time. A study in Frobisher Bay, Nunavut, also documented a decrease in bivalve abundances in 2016 compared to historical data from the years 1967 and 1976 despite an expected increase in abundances associated with increased food availability (Herder et al., 2022). Young Sound has very low levels of pelagic primary production (Rysgaard et al., 1999) and an increase in primary productivity associated with a longer open water period has not been documented thus far, likely due to increased light attenuation from higher turbidity resulting from increased terrestrial and glacial runoff (coastal darkening), as well as increased stratification limiting nutrient exchange from bottom waters (Holding et al., 2019; Maar et al., 2025). These parameters, as well as food quality and quantity were not directly addressed in the current study, only indirectly through the increased open water period, so the suggested mechanisms above and below warrant further study.

Food availability and carbon sourcing are generally considered main drivers of benthic biomass and production, and changes to them could drive the altered community structure observed in Young Sound. Food quantity is suggested to influence benthic abundances, whereas food quality affects benthic composition (Campanyà-Llovet et al., 2017). In addition, sympagic algae are considered a major source of organic matter to benthos along the coast and shelf of Northeast Kalaallit Nunaat, with ~90% of the assimilated carbon available from phytoplankton and ice algae in benthos estimated to have sympagic rather than phytoplankton origin (Cautain et al., 2024). The longer open water period might change the concentration and timing of sympagic algae to benthos, potentially leading to an altered carbon source and timing in food availability to benthos. Although previous studies have shown that sea-ice algae production in Young Sound is negligible due to the thick snow cover and general sea-ice characteristics (Rysgaard et al., 2001; Rysgaard and Nielsen, 2006), Holding et al. (2019) recorded a strong under-ice bloom in 2014 with primary production reaching $628 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, far above the average of $92 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ documented over the study period. Sea-ice algae have a higher sinking rate than phytoplankton, reaching benthos as a less degraded, higher-quality food source (Campanyà-Llovet et al., 2017). Although alternative, terrestrial sources of carbon comprise a substantial proportion of the carbon flux in Young Sound (Rysgaard and Sejr, 2007), a recent study found pelagic and sedimentary particulate organic matter, followed by benthic sources as the primary food source of benthos (Bridier et al., 2021a).

Benthic algae are a significant source of primary production in Young Sound, with estimates of benthic gross primary production

down to 40m comprising twice that of the pelagic production, making benthic primary production the most important source of primary production in the shallow outer parts of the fjord (Attard et al., 2016). A study of coastal benthos in the Beaufort Sea likewise found benthic primary production to be an important carbon source to benthos (Mctigue et al., 2015). Our study documented consistently high microphytobenthos concentrations across time and space, whereas foliose macroalgae displayed a more variable percentage cover throughout the study period, likely due to their patchy distribution associated with the availability of hard substrate. Large patches of partially degraded macroalgae and detritus were evident throughout the fjord (pers. obs.) down to great depths and far inside the fjord close to both river and glacial runoff sources, which attracted many grazers. Increased wave action could lead to more dislocated seaweed, as has been documented in Svalbard fjords (Renaud et al., 2015a). This raises questions of how tight the benthic-pelagic coupling is in Young Sound, and potentially other low-production fjords in the Arctic, as there are indications of a weakened coupling in the region (Cautain et al., 2024). Weaker benthic-pelagic coupling was observed in a previous study in Young Sound during periods with high stratification, which increased the macroalgal contribution of POM, whereas periods with lower stratification provided fresher pelagic organic matter of higher quality (Bridier et al., 2021a). This mechanism is hypothesized to explain the different community structure between years with long and short open water period, with some of the taxa potentially being better adapted to a specific source of carbon, while others could be adapted to a range of sources. How tight the benthic-pelagic coupling is in Young Sound, and more generally, in low-production Arctic fjords, needs to be further investigated.

Interestingly, our results suggest that the response in benthos to increased open water period differed between substrate types and occurred without a time lag. The communities associated with a shorter open water period and a higher proportion of hard substrate were characterized by typical hard-substrate fauna such as ascidians, anemones, and limpets, which could be more sensitive to climate change due to their limited mobility, hindering their movement to more favorable environmental conditions (Vye et al., 2020) at deeper depths (Burrows et al., 2019) or further north (Kortsch et al., 2015). The close proximity to the fjord opening could expose benthos to a larger degree of shelf water, bringing warmer water and new species to the fjord as seen on the shelf for certain shrimp and fish population (Andrews et al., 2019). The immediate response in benthos to increased open water period is somewhat surprising as it could be assumed that such structural changes might rather occur over longer periods of time. The relatively rapid response is consistent with previous findings from the Makarov Strait in the Eastern Barents Sea where the duration of the ice-free period was the primary driver of changes in biodiversity and structure of macrozoobenthos (Pavlova et al., 2023). Similarly, a study from a soft-bottom benthic community in a cold-water fjord in Svalbard also found an immediate response to marine heat waves (Jorda-Molina et al., 2023), suggesting that soft-bottom communities might be faster to respond to the effects of climate warming than anticipated. Climate-induced regime shifts have been documented further south in East Kalaallit Nunaat (Heide-Jorgensen et al., 2023), and there are indications of ongoing

borealization of the NE Kalaallit Nunaat shelf (Husson et al., 2024). In our study site, the shallow sill at the mouth of Young Sound could be expected to limit water and species exchange from the outside compared to an unsilled fjord (Al-Hababbeh et al., 2020), thereby delaying the ecological response to increased inflow of warm water from the shelf.

4.3 Community functions over time

Changes to the functioning of the benthos can provide insights into the resilience of the community and can help predict the vulnerability of the system to future environmental changes (Armitage et al., 2024). The functional characterization of Young Sound benthos is typical of high arctic fjord communities, with small to medium sizes, relatively long lifespans, low mobility, and suspension and surface deposit feeding. Body size is considered an important master trait in ecology, and changes to this trait can influence energy transfer and carbon cycling (Górska and Włodarska-Kowalczyk, 2017). We found a dominance of small to medium sized taxa, similar to other epibenthic studies in nearby NE Kalaallit Nunaat fjords and shelf (Armitage et al., 2025) and the Chukchi Borderlands (Zhulay et al., 2021). Only in later years and during longer open water period, larger sized organisms occurred driven by *C. intestinalis* and Solasteridae, which could suggest a subtle shift in secondary production as a result of altered food availability. Small/medium sizes also increased slightly in the later years, something that could indicate a community shift towards faster-growing, opportunistic species. We also found a reduction in the average lifespan over time, driven by a decline in abundance of the long-lived bivalves *H. arctica* and *Mya* sp. The documented shortening of lifespan is consistent with other studies from Arctic epibenthos in Svalbard fjords impacted by increased sea-surface temperature and reduced sea-ice concentration (Al-Hababbeh et al., 2020) and the NE Kalaallit Nunaat shelf (Armitage et al., 2024). The longevity of invertebrates influences secondary production, carbon storage and cycling, and can also affect the vulnerability of the community to environmental change (Dinevik et al., 2025).

The benthic community in Young Sound displayed a variety of feeding habits, with filter/suspension feeding being the most common in shallow waters but decreasing in importance with depth. A previous study in Young Sound by Sejr et al. (2000) found deposit feeders to be the most common trait at all depths, a discrepancy with our findings likely due to differences in sampling. Interestingly, in our study, the filter/suspension feeding modality was reduced in year 2008 and the years 2021–2022 in the shallowest communities, coinciding with a longer open water period and increased runoff. This could indicate a shift in food availability/quality, favoring taxa with a different feeding mode, with a general increase in opportunist/scavenger and predator feeding guilds. Other studies from the region have found opportunist/scavengers and predators to be the most common in fjord systems (Armitage et al., 2025; Zhulay et al., 2021). The observed change in the feeding modality suggests that an increase in runoff and sedimentation may negatively impact filter/suspension feeders through clogging of feeding apparatus, as has been proposed in other studies (Beuchel and Gulliksen, 2008; Mcgovern et al., 2020).

4.4 Limitations

In this study of community structure in an Arctic fjord, samples collected from the same sites across different years were compared to assess temporal variability. However, some of the observed differences may reflect small-scale spatial heterogeneity in seafloor habitats, as it was not possible to collect samples from exactly identical locations during each sampling event. Consequently, part of the variability in community composition and biodiversity metrics likely arises from fine-scale differences in sediment characteristics, microtopography, and local environmental conditions rather than from true temporal changes.

In addition, the observed correlations between changes in benthic community structure and open water period and terrestrial runoff are likely indirect, as both sea ice dynamics and terrestrial inputs serve as broad indicators of shifts in multiple interrelated environmental parameters. Changes in sea ice and runoff influence a cascade of physical and biogeochemical processes, such as light availability, sedimentation rates, organic matter input, and water column stratification, that collectively shape benthic habitats and community structure. Therefore, the observed correlations should be interpreted as reflecting the complex, system-wide responses of the benthic ecosystem to a suite of environmental changes rather than direct causal effects of these single variables and the hypothesized mechanisms related to altered sedimentation, turbidity, food quality, and benthic-pelagic coupling warrant further study.

5 Conclusions

Despite changes in sea ice coverage and run-off we found only subtle changes in functional and taxonomic composition based on comparative surveys of the sea floor from 2003–2010 and 2020–2021. In contrast to coastal areas of Svalbard and SE Kalaallit Nunaat where large-scale inflow of Atlantic water has resulted in introduction of new Atlantic species, the absence of Atlantic inflow in Young Sound has resulted in a near-static species pool.

Although there is no indication of any regime shifts or other drastic changes to community structure, as is the case further south in Kalaallit Nunaat (Heide-Jorgensen et al., 2023) and in Svalbard fjords (Kortsch et al., 2012), we documented subtle indications of climate-induced community change through altered abundances of some taxa, and the occurrence of the ascidian *C. intestinalis*.

Bivalves constitute the majority of benthic biomass in Young Sound and are essential to higher trophic levels in the area such as walrus (Born et al., 2003) and eider ducks. Future changes in bivalve biomass and composition are likely to have cascading effects on these higher trophic level species as has been observed elsewhere in the Arctic (Richman and Lovvorn, 2003). Suspension feeders support benthic-pelagic coupling (Dinevik et al., 2025), and a shift in the prevalence of this trait would affect ecosystem functioning.

For the future, we urgently recommend the continuation of the benthic time series as part of the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring program and/or Atlantic-Distributed Biological Observatory. Such monitoring can efficiently be achieved using under-water

imagery as an appropriate balance of time required and meaningful taxonomic resolution. On occasion, physical identification from vouchers and food web links via trophic marker analysis will add taxonomic resolution and confirm ecological interactions and carbon sourcing.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/Supplementary Material. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Ethics statement

The manuscript presents research on animals that do not require ethical approval for their study.

Author contributions

AA-H: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. BB: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. RP: Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Methodology. MS: Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Supplementary material

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